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Labor Productivity in OECD Countries

Between 2000 and 2021 it grew by an average of 35.87%

The OECD calculates the value of labor productivity. The indicator is obtained by dividing the gross domestic product by the number of hours worked. The value is expressed in dollars.

Ranking of OECD countries by labor productivity in 2021. Ireland leads by value of labor productivity with a value equal to 128.2 units, followed by Luxembourg with an amount equal to 99 units and Norway with a value equal to 84.4 units. In the middle of the ranking are Canada with a value equal to 53.6 units, Turkey with a value equal to 53.1 units and Spain with a value equal to 51.8 units. Chile closes the ranking with a value of 29, followed by Mexico with an amount of 19.5 and Colombia with a value of 14.3 units. On average, the value of hourly labor productivity in 2021 was equal to an amount of \$56.35 in OECD countries.

Ranking of OECD countries by percentage change in hourly productivity between 2000 and 2020. Latvia is in first place by value of percentage change in hourly productivity with a change equal to an amount of 237.9% equal to an amount of 24, 7 units, followed by Ireland with a value equal to 225.66% equal to an amount of 73.8 units and by Lithuania with a value equal to 221.66% equal to an amount of 26.2 units. In the middle of the table are Australia with a value equal to 119.91% equal to an amount of 13.1 units, followed by Denmark with a value equal to an amount of 116.33% equal to an amount of 15.8 units, followed by Austria with a value equal to 114.73% equal to an amount of 13.8 units. The ranking is closed by Luxembourg with a value equal to 91.54% equal to an amount of 1.5 units, followed by Greece with a value equal to 85.95% equal to an amount of -1.4 units and by Mexico with a value equal to 85.59% equal to an amount of -0.9 units. On average, the percentage change for OECD countries between 2000 and 2020 in productivity per hour worked grew by 136.24%, equal to an amount of 14.87 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm is performed below with the Silhouette coefficient. The following clusters are identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Australia, Canada, Spain, Japan, Colombia, Mexico, Greece, Chile, New Zealand, Slovenia, Turkey, Israel, Portugal, Latvia, Slovakia, North Korea, Czech Republic, Lithuania, Poland, Hungary, Estonia.
- Cluster 2: Denmark, Switzerland, Sweden, Belgium, Netherlands, United States, Austria, France, Germany, Norway, Finland, Luxembourg, United Kingdom, Iceland, Italy.

Overall, if we consider the value of the median, the following ordering of the clusters results: $C2=71.6 > C1=43.3$.

Network Analysis with Mahattan distance. A network analysis using the Manhattan distance is presented below. The following complex network structure is identified, namely:

- The United States has a connection with Sweden for a value equal to 0.27 and with Austria for a value equal to 0.36 units;
- Sweden has a connection with the United States for a value equal to 0.27 units, with Austria for a value equal to 0.28 and with the Netherlands for a value equal to 0.39 units;

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- The Netherlands has a connection with Sweden equal to an amount of 0.39 units, with Austria for an amount equal to 0.39 units;
- Austria has a connection with Sweden worth 0.28 units, with the United States worth 0.36 units, with the Netherlands worth 0.39 units, with Germany for a value equal to 0.35 units, and with France for a value equal to 0.29 units;
- Germany has a connection with Austria for a value equal to 0.35 units and with France for a value equal to 0.21;
- France has a connection with Austria worth 0.29 and with Germany worth 0.21.

There is a complex network structure between Spain, Canada and Australia, in particular:

- Canada has a connection with Spain for a value equal to 0.21 units, and with Australia for a value equal to 0.28 units;
- Spain has a connection with Australia for a value equal to 0.31 units and with Canada for a value equal to 0.21 units;
- Australia has a connection with Spain worth 0.31 units and with Canada worth 0.28 units.

There is a connection between Poland, South Korea, Estonia, Lithuania as below namely:

- Poland has a connection with South Korea equal to a value of 0.25 units and with Estonia with a value equal to 0.26 units;
- South Korea has a connection with Poland equal to a value of 0.25 units, and with Estonia par a value equal to 0.33 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Poland worth 0.26, with South Korea worth 0.33, and with Lithuania worth 0.27.

There is a complex network structure between Slovenia, Israel, Portugal and New Zealand. Particularly:

- Portugal has a connection with Israel worth 0.35 units and with New Zealand worth 0.38 units;
- New Zealand has a connection with Israel equal to a value of 0.36 units and with Portugal equal to an amount of 0.38 units;
- Israel has a connection with Portugal with a value equal to 0.35 units, with New Zealand equal to an amount of 0.36 and with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.33 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Israel equal to the amount of 0.33 units.

In addition, the following simplified relations exist, namely:

- United Kingdom and Finland are connected with a value equal to 0.32 units;
- Switzerland and Belgium are connected for a value equal to 0.22 units;
- Slovakia and the Czech Republic have a connection equal to the amount of 0.32 units.

Conclusions. The value of GDP per hour worked in OECD countries has grown from \$41.47 in 2000 to a value of \$56.34 in 2021 with a change of \$14.87 equal to a growth of 35.87%. Although labor productivity has grown significantly, there is still a significant difference between the various OECD countries. In 2021 the value of GDP per hour worked was equal to an amount of 128.2 dollars in Ireland while the same value in Colombia was equal to 14.3 dollars. It should be considered that technology and human capital training should significantly increase the value of GDP per hour worked. However, aging populations in many OECD countries and difficulties in implementing new technologies are likely to reduce future GDP growth per hour worked.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l., prof. Alberto Costantiello and prof. Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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Appendix

Pil per Ora Lavorata nel 2021. Fonte: OCSE					
Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	Ireland	128,2	20	Spain	51,8
2	Luxembourg	99	21	Slovak Republic	48,1
3	Norway	84,4	22	Israel	47,6
4	Switzerland	76,6	23	Japan	47,3
5	Denmark	75,8	24	Slovenia	47,1
6	United States	74,8	25	Lithuania	46,1
7	Sweden	73,7	26	Czech Republic	43,5
8	Belgium	73,6	27	New Zealand	43,3
9	Austria	69,6	28	Estonia	42,9
10	Germany	68,3	29	Korea	42,9
11	Netherlands	67,7	30	Poland	42
12	Iceland	66,8	31	Latvia	41,4
13	France	66,7	32	Portugal	40,5
14	Finland	61,9	33	Hungary	39,9
15	United Kingdom	59,1	34	Greece	33,2
16	Australia	56,9	35	Chile	29
17	Italy	54,6	36	Mexico	19,5
18	Canada	53,6	37	Colombia	14,3
19	Türkiye	53,1			

Variazione Percentuale PIL per Ora Lavorata							
Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var per
1	Latvia	24,7	237,9	20	Austria	13,8	114,73
2	Ireland	73,8	225,66	21	Switzerland	14,9	114,15
3	Lithuania	26,2	221,66	22	New Zealand	8,2	113,36
4	Korea	23	205,58	23	Germany	12,2	111,75
5	Türkiye	26,9	192,67	24	Japan	8,3	111,28
6	Estonia	21,7	192,36	25	Canada	9,4	111,27
7	Slovak Republic	24,1	190,42	26	Portugal	7,1	111,26
8	Poland	19,8	179,19	27	Finland	10,6	110,66
9	Czech Republic	17,5	157,31	28	Belgium	10,5	106,64
10	Hungary	15,6	154,2	29	France	9,5	106,61
11	Chile	11,1	152,01	30	United Kingdom	8,2	106,11
12	Iceland	23,8	145,35	31	Spain	6,8	105,11
13	Slovenia	15,8	140,48	32	Norway	11	104,99
14	Colombia	4,6	137,42	33	Netherlands	8	103,4
15	Israel	14,4	133,37	34	Italy	1,8	93,41
16	United States	20,3	127,25	35	Luxembourg	1,5	91,54
17	Sweden	18,7	124	36	Greece	-1,4	85,95
18	Australia	13,1	119,91	37	Mexico	-0,9	85,59
19	Denmark	15,8	116,33				

